

**On the taxonomic rank of *Cerambyx klinzigi* Podaný, 1964
(Coleoptera, Cerambycidae)**

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Abstract: The rank of *Cerambyx cerdo klinzigi* Podaný, 1964 is upgraded to species as *Cerambyx klinzigi* Podaný, 1964 following Özdikmen & Turgut (2009). The distinguishing characters and color illustrations are proposed.

Introduction

Cerambyx cerdo klinzigi Podaný, 1964 was described from “Caucase” without exact locality data on the bases of a single peculiar male. Such situation against the backdrop of widespread distribution throughout the whole Caucasus of *C. cerdo acuminatus* Motschulsky, 1853 has given rise to conflicting interpretations of the name in the literature.

***Cerambyx klinzigi* Podaný, 1964**

Figs 1-2

Cerambyx cerdo klinzigi Podaný, 1964: 88 - “Caucase, leg. Leder”; Miroshnikov, 2010: 44 - “Caucase”; Vartanis, 2018: 77 - “Georgia (Caucasus)”; Sláma, 2019: 203 - “Caucasus”.

Cerambyx klinzigi, Özdikmen & Turgut: 2009: 308 - “Caucasus”.

Cerambyx cerdo, Miroshnikov, 2010: 43, 45 (? = *cerdo klinzigi* Podany, 1964), 46-47.

Cerambyx cerdo cerdo, Löbl & Smetana, 2010: 159 (= *acuminatus* Motschulsky = *heros* Scopoli, 1763 = *iranicus* Heyrovský, 1951 = *klinzigi* Podaný = *manderstjaernae* Mulsant & Godart, 1855 = *pfisteri* Stierlin, 1864).

Cerambyx [?] *cerdo klinzigi*, Miroshnikov, 2011: 11, 28.

Cerambyx (s. str.) *cerdo acuminatus*, Danilevsky, 2020: 71, 215 (= *klinzigi* Podaný).

Type material. Holotype, male, “Caucase” - Slovenské národné muzeum, Bratislava.

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A single male is known; body rather wide, nearly parallel sided, in *C. cerdo* Linnaeus, 1758 (Fig. 3) body narrow with sides strongly converging posteriorly; male antennae very long, extend beyond elytral apex with three joints; 3rd-5th antennal joints distinctly thicker and shorter, elytral punctation much finer, dots don't conjugate forming vermiform sculpture, elytral veins indistinct, legs thicker, tibiae distinctly curved, spines of elytral apices nearly indistinct; body length: 44 mm, width: 13 mm.

Comments.

Many authors (Podaný, 1964; Miroshnikov, 2010; Löbl & Smetana, 2010; Vartanis, 2018; Sláma, 2019; Danilevsky, 2020) regarded the holotype as unusual representative of *C. cerdo*, but *C. klinzigi* differs by too many systems of characters.

In fact, populations consisting of peculiar specimens of *C. cerdo* are known. According to personal message (2024) by M. Slama, small populations of *C. cerdo cerdo* m. *laevicollis* Heyrovský, 1955 (with smooth pronotum) are known from near Třeboň (Czech Republic) and preserved in the collection of Leopold Seichert. Such populations could be accepted as a geographical form inside subspecies, that is impossible after modern Code of Zoological Nomenclature.

According to Miroshnikov (2010: 46), J. Voříček was personally convinced, that *C. klinzigi* Podaný, 1964 was later described as *C. heinzianus* Demelt, 1976, but Miroshnikov (2010: 46) could not agree with that opinion, and listed several compelling arguments. In fact, *C. heinzianus* is quite a different species. Finally, Miroshnikov (2010: 47) regarded species rank for *C. cerdo klinzigi* as rather probable.

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Fig. 1. *Cerambyx klinzigi* Podaný, 1964: holotype, male, “Caucase” (photo by RNDr. V. Jansky, Slovenské národné museum, Bratislava).

Fig. 2. Set of the holotype labels of *Cerambyx cerdo klinzigi* Podaný, 1964 (photos by RNDr. V. Jansky, Slovenské národné museum, Bratislava).

Fig. 3. *Cerambyx cerdo acutispinum* Motschulsky, 1853: male, Armenia, Megri, 30.6.2003, M. Danilevsky leg. (collection of M. Danilevsky).

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